

Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for
High Performance Bioseparations

DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

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Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP)

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University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

University of Bayreuth, Bayreuth, Germany

Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Lisbon, Portugal

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0.2	28/09/21	NOVA	Final complete version
0.3	28/09/21	NOVA	Validation
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Abbreviations/Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	
DEP	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
PURE	Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for High Performance Bioseparations
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
WP	Work Package
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
IP	Intellectual property
FET-Open	Future and Emerging Technologies Open
PT	Portugal
DE	Germany
NOVA	Project Partner from the NOVA University Lisbon
BOKU	Project Partner from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna
BAYREUTH	Project partner from the University of Bayreuth
IBET	Project Partner from the Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation – European Union

Executive Summary

The following document is the Deliverable 5.4 “Dissemination and Exploitation Plan” (DEP) of the PURE Project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement Number 899732.

This document is the first version of the DEP, consisting of preliminary information regarding the actions taken by the Consortium and the Coordinator to meet the obligations on dissemination and exploitation decided in the Grant Agreement. The dissemination and exploitation plans are reported, along with the stakeholder and impact analyses, the guidelines and monitoring of the dissemination and exploitation activities. The project’s Data Management and Intellectual Property Rights Plans are also considered and bound to the DEP.

The DEP is expected to develop during the project duration, therefore updated versions of this document will be made available over the project execution.

I Introduction

The EU-funded PURE project aims to develop precisely functionalised adsorbents using principles of scalable biotechnological processes. Affinity ligands will be introduced into convective adsorbents in a site-directed oriented manner and predefined spatial arrangement. The project has brought together an interdisciplinary team of leading scientists from academia and industry with expertise in biology, chemistry, computational modelling, materials science, bioprocess engineering and applied social sciences.

The plan to disseminate PURE's project includes: i) dissemination of the results to scientific audiences, targeting experienced and young researchers; ii) disseminate project results among national/European authorities (that may benefit from PURE's technology) and industrial stakeholders. Data management will be done according to FAIR data principles, and PURE will follow open access guidelines for publications.

The DEP is part of the WP5 and the deliverable 5.4 of the PURE project.

2. GUIDELINES FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

2.1 Definitions and guidelines for dissemination and exploitation activities

According to the European Commission H2020 Online Manual on Grant management, Disseminations and Exploitation of project results are defined as following:

- Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers). By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.
- Exploitation is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking.

2.2 Open access to scientific publications and research data

The open access to scientific publications and research data in the PURE project follows the EU guideline for FAIR data. The PURE project will follow the principles of its Data Management Plan (DMP, doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5503931), consisting of information regarding the type and format of data that will be collected and generated, its origin, data utility and how PURE project research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (i.e. FAIR).

The purpose of DMP is to provide the members of the consortium with an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy regarding all the datasets generated by the project.

2.3 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

The communication and dissemination activities within the PURE project will identify that the project has obtained funding from the European Commission and display it according to the indications on the European commission manual for FET-Open projects. Publications and other dissemination material include the following, as acknowledgement that the work was generated with the financial support of the EC:

The Pure project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program under grant agreement No. 899732

2.4 Compliance with general data protection regulation (GDPR)

The EU GDPR 2016/679 is a regulation in the EU's law on data protection and privacy for all individuals within the EU, entered into force on 25 May 2018. In compliance with the EU GDPR, the Consortium is committed to protect the privacy of the users of the project website. Both personal and non-personal information collected is protected according to the highest privacy and data protection standards and best practices.

Information about data collection, storage, usage and purposes has been already documented in the PURE'e Data Management Plan (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5503931).

3 DISSEMINATION PLAN

3.1 Agreements on dissemination

The dissemination of the project results will follow the principles agreed by all project partners in the Grant Agreement. It will also follow the principles for open data as reported in the Data Management Plan (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5503931).

3.2 Stakeholder and impact analyses

The stakeholder and impact analysis are currently ongoing for the PURE project, in WP5. A team from NOVA is dedicated to analysing the impact of the project with stakeholders, during its execution D5.3.

3.3 Dissemination plan

The plan to disseminate PURE’s project includes: i) dissemination of the results to scientific audiences, targeting experienced and young researchers; ii) disseminate project results among national/European authorities (that may benefit from PURE’s technology) and industrial stakeholders. Data management will be done according to FAIR data principles, and PURE will follow open access guidelines for publications. The detailed actions are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Dissemination activities. *KPI: Key Performance Indicator; IS: industry stakeholders; SC: Scientific Community*

Channel	Period	Audience	KPI	Goal
High-impact & open access publications (e.g. Nature Communications; Nature Materials; Advanced Materials; Biotech & Bioeng)	M9–M48	SC	8	Publish results and make them available; researchers’ career promotion
Scientific conferences (e.g. Gordon Research Conferences; ESBES, ECAB & ECB meetings; Applied SynBio; European Materials Symposium)	M12-M48	SC	16	Disseminate results among peers; create awareness; researchers’ career promotion (e.g. oral and poster presentations)
Open Research Data deposit (e.g. GenBank, DSMZ, Addgene, Europe pmc plus; protein data bank)	M3-M48	SC	10	Re-evaluation of data; promote scientific advance (sequence data; SAXS and multiscale models; fiber properties)
Winter schools	M24 & 48	SC	2; 2 days	Training of young researchers (25 participants)
Newsletters	M3-M48	SC & IS	2	Visibility of the project (sent to 1000 contacts)

3.4 Monitoring of dissemination activities

Dissemination activities will be monitored yearly by NOVA with the collaboration of all consortium partners. They will be reported in the project’s annual report.

3.5 Communication plan

The plan to communicate PURE’s project includes actions that target distinct audiences (Table 2). The actions targeting the general public will be directed to adults and young adults, children and teenagers. Communication actions will give a particular emphasis on the science behind the project, the relevance of the interdisciplinary approach and the impact of PURE’s technology in our daily lives. PURE’s team believes that the project has all the necessary ingredients for original communication activities, namely videos and a theatre play.

Table 2: Communication activities. *KPI: Key Performance Indicator; GP: general public*

Channel	Period	Audience	KPI	Goal
Website	M3-M48	GP	>2000 visits	Promotion of the project
Social media (e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter)	M1-M48	GP, business networks	1500 followers	Promotion of the project; visibility of results; science outreach
Public science events (e.g. European Researchers Night, Open days)	M6-M48	GP	8 participations 1000 visitors	Promotion of the project; science outreach
Theatre show	M6-M48	GP (children, teenagers, families)	8 performances 800 spectators	Promotion of the project; science outreach
Videos	M6-M48	GP (adults, teenagers, young adults)	3 videos, 3000 visits	Promotion of the project; science outreach
Visits to Schools	M6-M48	GP (children, teenagers)	4 visits, 400 students	Promotion of the project; science outreach
Press releases	M1-M48	GP, media	8 press releases 24 published news in mass media	Promotion of the project; visibility of results; visibility of scientific publications

4 EXPLOITATION PLAN

4.1 Agreements on exploitation

Exploitation of the PURE project results among the consortium, will follow the guideline of the project Grant Agreement and the IPR Plan, already agreed and approved by all consortium partners.

4.2 Exploitation Plan and exploitation activities

The plan for exploitation includes IP management and the design of a roadmap for future development of the project. Partners hold relevant patents on their technologies and, therefore, clear rules are defined on the ownership of foreground, background and sideground IP (also joint ownerships); the assignment of IP; the access to IPR and a policy to disclose generated R&D results among partners, Advisory Board and other potentially interested stakeholders. These follow the Consortium Agreement and NDAs established with the Advisory Board members. For the exploitation of results, the partner iBET will be actively involved in the transfer of technology to the society, namely through the development of research projects with private and public organization and in the commercialization of services related with their market interests. The industrial partners of the Advisory Board will also play a relevant role in this action, encouraged to promote PURE throughout their network. Planned exploitation activities are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Exploitation activities. *KPI: Key Performance Indicator; IS: industry stakeholders; SC: Scientific Community*

Channel	Period	Audience	KPI	Goal
Protection of generated IP	M18-M48	IS	1	Later commercial exploitation
Industry-oriented conferences & fairs (e.g. European Summit of Industrial Biotech)	M12-M48	IS	3	Promotion of the project; identify industrial partners for exploitation (50 partnering, 3 presentations/posters; 500 visitors)
Interviews, questionnaires & meetings with industry (alternative bioseparation markets)	M9-M48	IS	10	Tune technology & product attributes; design a roadmap for future developments; create a collaboration framework model
Identification of funding for follow-up projects	M18-M48	Funding Agencies; IS	>2	Identification of funding opportunities to follow-up successful results after the project is finished

4.3 Intellectual property right and innovation management

Intellectual property rights and innovation methods will follow the PURE's IPR plan and Grant Agreement, which were verified and accepted by all project partners.

4.4 Monitoring of exploitation activities

Exploitation activities will be monitored yearly by NOVA with the collaboration of all consortium partners. They will be reported in the project's annual report.

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